

Samanatham Tank: Conservation and Protection

Surendran Appasamy & ¹Joseph Thatheyus Antony

¹Email: ajt@americancollege.edu.in

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14686339>

Abstract

As essential elements of the global hydrological cycle, lakes offer a wide range of benefits to society, including access to freshwater, fostering biodiversity and offering recreational opportunities. However, anthropogenic influences and climate change significantly threaten lake ecosystems, leading to their degradation and a decline in ecological functions. The present study emphasizes the critical need for the conservation and protection of Samantham Tank in Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India. It identifies various threats to the tank, such as pollution, eutrophication, invasive species, and habitat loss. Additionally, the study delves into ecological and socioeconomic impacts of lake degradation, including water scarcity, decline in biodiversity and detrimental impacts on local communities. To confront these challenges, the study recommends the implementation of sustainable management practices.

Key words: Fresh water, Lake, Reservoir, Protection, Madurai

Introduction

Wetlands are characterized by their water levels, which remain close to or above the ground for most of the year. The historical link between humans and wetlands is longstanding, with early civilizations emerging in wetland environments like the Indus floodplains, the Nile Delta and the Tigris-Euphrates Fertile Crescent (Wilson, 2020; Matsumoto et al.2023).

Globally, wetlands account for about 6% of the land surface and include various types such as marshes, swamps, lagoons, bogs, pools, puddles and mangroves. These ecosystems are among the most biologically productive, supporting a rich diversity of fauna and flora, making them both valuable and vulnerable natural resources on the planet (Guo et al., 2017; Sharma et al., 2021; Chakraborty et al., 2023).

The wetland ecosystems of India are extensive and vary across different geographical landscapes. Many of these wetlands are interconnected with major river systems such as the Ganges, Cauvery, Krishna, Godavari, and Tapti. India has a total of 27,403 wetlands, which include 23,444 inland and 3,959 coastal wetlands. As reported in the Directory of Asian Wetlands (1989), wetlands account for 18.4% of the nation's area (excluding rivers), with 70% of this area dedicated to paddy farming. Out of an estimated 4.1 million hectares of wetlands (excluding agricultural lands, rivers, and streams), 1.5 million hectares are classified as natural, while 2.6 million hectares are artificial. Coastal wetlands cover around 6,750 square kilometers and are primarily characterized by mangrove forests. Approximately 80% of the mangrove population is located in the Sunderbans of West Bengal and the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, with the remainder found in coastal regions of Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala, Goa, Maharashtra and Gujarat. The wetlands found in southern peninsular India are primarily artificial, commonly known as yeris or

tanks. These water bodies are established in nearly every village, fulfilling various human water needs and serving as important nesting, feeding, and breeding grounds for a diverse range of bird species. Some of the prominent natural wetland locations in South India include Point Calimere in Tamil Nadu, Ashtamudi, Sasthamkotta, and Vembanad lakes in Kerala, along with Kolleru Lake in Andhra Pradesh. These wetland systems are vital for the livelihoods of countless individuals, offering a range of goods and services. They play a significant role in flood management, coastal erosion control, and disaster risk reduction, particularly during cyclones and tidal waves, while also providing long-term water storage (Shan et al., 2021; Pradhan et al., 2023).

The current research presents a brief assessment of the Samatham tank's status in Madurai city, Tamil Nadu, India. It also explores potential avenues for increasing the lake's water storage capacity. In addition, the study endeavors to establish a comprehensive framework for sustainable management, integrating participatory strategies.

Fig.1. Geographical Location of Samanatham Tank, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

(Source: Google Map)

Fig.2. Multifaceted Outlook of Samanatham Tank, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Study Area - Samanatham Tank

Samanatham Tank is located in Thiruparankundram Block of Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India (Fig. 1 & 2). It ranges from 9.866674° N to 78.14719 E. This region experiences tropical climatic conditions with the average rainfall of 800 mm. The rainy season is October and November while the temperature ranges between 20°C to 38°C. The winter is mild while the summer is hot and humid.

Observations and Inferences

Lakes serve as vital water bodies, offering essential water supplies even in areas without nearby rivers or streams. They greatly enhance the local landscape's natural beauty and provide a habitat for various plants and animals, fostering a healthy ecosystem. Lakes can be classified into different types based on several factors, with most being freshwater bodies that accumulate rainwater rather than seawater. This characteristic makes them indispensable for providing fresh drinking water and supporting agricultural irrigation.

The Samanatham Tank area includes wetlands, agricultural land,

vegetation such as trees and grasses, and open search-type habitats. The tree species in this area mainly include *Azadirachta indica* (Neem), *Mangifera indica* (Mango), *Ficus benghalensis* (Banyan), *Acacia nilotica* (Babul), and *Tamarindus indica* (Tamarind). Flowering plants such as *Jasminum officinale* (Jasmine), *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* (China rose), and *Nelumbo nucifera* (Lotus) are also found here. The area is dominated by the invasive plant *Prosopis juliflora* (Mesquite). Aquatic plants in the wetland area include *Eichhornia crassipes* (Water hyacinth), *Hydrilla verticillata* (Hydrilla), *Nymphaea* spp. (Water lilies), and *Typha* spp. (Cattails) (Fig. 3).

Fig.3. Aquatic Plants

Fish species observed during the study included *Catla catla* (Indian carp), *Cirrhinus mrigala* (Mirghal), *Labeo rohita* (Rohu), *Oreochromis*

mossambicus (Tilapia), *Channa striata* (Snakehead murrel), and *Lepidocephalichthys thermalis* (Common spiny loach).

Fig.4. Aquatic Birds

The Samanatham Tank area is home to various animals, including toads, water snakes, and turtles. Bird species (Fig. 4) commonly observed include *Anas crecca* (Common Teal), *Anas poecilorhyncha* (Indian Spot-billed Duck), *Phoenicopterus roseus* (Greater Flamingo), *Columba livia* (Rock Dove), *Apus affinis* (Little Swift), *Eudynamis scolopaceus* (Common Koel), *Pavo cristatus* (Indian Peafowl), *Mycteria leucocephala* (Painted Stork), *Pelecanus philippensis* (Spot-billed Pelican), *Nycticorax nycticorax* (Black-crowned Night Heron), *Bubulcus ibis* (Cattle Egret), *Ardeola grayii* (Indian Pond Heron), *Microcarbo niger* (Little Cormorant), *Athene brama* (Spotted Owlet), *Alcedo atthis* (Common Kingfisher),

Dicrurus macrocercus (Black Drongo), *Corvus splendens* (House Crow), *Corvus macrorhynchos* (Large-billed Crow), *Terpsiphone paradisi* (Indian Paradise-flycatcher), *Passer domesticus* (House Sparrow), *Orthotomus sutorius* (Common Tailorbird), *Acridotheres tristis* (Common Myna), and *Pastor roseus* (Rosy Starling).

Bird identification was supported by field guides focused on Indian subcontinent birds, as well as a comprehensive book on Indian birds. Each species was given standardized common and scientific nomenclature (Grimmett et al., 2011; Praveen et al., 2016; Jeyalakshmi et al., 2023). Despite being an artificial aquatic system, Samanatham Tank supports rich biodiversity and contributes to flood control and water management in the local region. Conservation measures are essential to protect this ecosystem, with the potential to develop it into a bird sanctuary. Some bird species here are classified as vulnerable or near-threatened, while many are of "Least Concern." During annual migrations, Samanatham Tank could attract thousands of birds each year,

including pelicans, ducks, and storks.

However, disturbances to this ecosystem include tree felling for road expansion, construction of the outer ring road (Fig. 5), and burning of waste materials nearby (Fig. 6). Additionally,

the spread of *Prosopis juliflora* (Mesquite) may not support bird breeding, as its branching pattern is unsuitable for the nests of many species. Other disruptions include poaching and fishing activities.

Fig.5. Construction of road near the Samanatham tank

Fig.6. Burning of waste materials in the surroundings of Samanatham tank

Conclusion

Safeguarding and conserving Samanatham Tank is essential for maintaining ecological balance, enhancing biodiversity, and ensuring the availability of freshwater resources. Effective water management practices are pivotal in achieving these goals. By implementing measures such as pollution reduction, sedimentation control, and water level management, we can protect the health and vitality of this ecosystem. Sustainable approaches, including responsible land use planning, wastewater management, and public awareness initiatives, are crucial to prevent further degradation and promote long-term sustainability. Additionally, investing in research and monitoring programs is vital for understanding the complex interactions within the Samanatham Tank ecosystem and for developing informed conservation strategies. Cooperation among governments, communities, and environmental organizations is key to addressing the challenges that lakes face and ensuring their future well-being.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the authorities of the American College,

Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India for the facilities and encouragement.

References

- Chakraborty, S. K., Sanyal, P., and Ray, R. (2023). *Wetlands Ecology: Eco-biological Uniqueness of a Ramsar Site (East Kolkata Wetlands, India)*. Springer Nature.
- Grimmett, R., C. Inskipp and T. Inskipp, 2011. *Birds of the Indian Subcontinent*. 2nd Edn., Christopher Helm, London, United Kingdom, ISBN: 9781408127636, Pages: 528.
- Guo, M., Li, J., Sheng, C., Xu, J., and Wu, L. (2017). A review of wetland remote sensing. *Sensors*, 17(4), 777.
- Jeyalakshmi G, Surendran A and Thatheyus AJ. (2023). Diversity of Birds in Tamilnadu Agriculture College and Research Institute Campus, Madurai, Tamilnadu, India. *Asian Journal of Biological Sciences*, 16(4): 485-492.
- Matsumoto, M., Miller, C., and Smith, C. (2023). *Early River Valley Civilizations and the Near East. He Huaka'i Honua:*

- Journeys in World History I, to 1500 CE Honolulu CC HIST 151.
- Pradhan, C., Chembolu, V., Bharti, R., and Dutta, S. (2023). Regulated rivers in India: Research Aprogress and future directions. ISH Journal of Hydraulic Engineering, 29(1), 58-70.
- Praveen, J., R. Jayapal and A. Pittie, 2016. A checklist of the birds of India. Indian Birds, 11: 113-165.
- Shan, V., Singh, S. K., and Haritash, A. K. (2021). Present status, conservation, and management of wetlands in India. In Advances in Energy and Environment: Select Proceedings of TRACE 2020 (pp. 235-256). Springer Singapore.
- Sharma, S., Phartiyal, M., Madhav, S., and Singh, P. (2021). Global wetlands: categorization, distribution and global scenario. Wetlands Conservation: Current Challenges and Future Strategies, 1-16.
- Wilson, B. (2020). Metropolis: A History of Humankind's Greatest Invention. Random House.

About the Authors

The first author, **Dr. Surendran Appasamy** is an Assistant Professor in the Department of Biochemistry at The American College, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

The second author, **Dr. Joseph Thatheyus Antony** is Head and Associate Professor in the Department of Microbiology at The American College, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India.